

Revitalizing Pedagogical Instructions Towards An Improved Grammatical Competence

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Abstract. The study explored the challenges English teachers face in improving the grammar competence of junior high school students. This study employed a phenomenological research design to determine the experiences and perceptions of the eight (8) participants. The themes of teachers' challenges in improving students' grammatical competence were poor attitude toward grammar instructions, diverse learning needs, and limited vocabulary. Meanwhile, the themes of teachers coping strategies were presenting grammar knowledge in rich and real contexts, enhancing the systematicity, relevance, and fun of grammar teaching, and pointing out students' errors skillfully. Lastly, on the educational management insights, the themes were sustained practice, cultivating a love for reading, and instilling a positive learning environment. Integrating these themes places students at the center of the learning experience. It acknowledges their diverse learning needs, fosters engagement, and encourages a positive attitude toward learning grammar. Teachers could empower students by creating an engaging, relevant, and supportive learning environment to manage the challenges of improving grammatical competence with enthusiasm and resilience. Moreover, the results provided comprehensive data for future research with similar scope. Future researchers may research innovative teaching methods, technology integration, and multimodal approaches that can provide valuable insights. They may also explore the influence of cultural and linguistic factors on grammatical competence. This study may be published in a reputable research journal.

KEY WORDS

1. grammar competence
2. English curriculum challenges
3. teaching pedagogy

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1. Introduction

Grammar is regarded as one of the fundamentals of language. Regardless of any language, competence in grammar is foundational to one's ability to communicate in a particular language. One's good grasp of grammar implies the ability to send clearer messages and the likelihood of being intelligible and understood by others. With these concerns, teachers with pedagogical skills are very critical to achieving this desire. The pedagogical skills can make evaluations

and assessments that precisely reflect the learning results of their students. This way, they can assess students' progress and distinguish regions where further guidance is required. According to Bradshaw (2013), in the global context, one can also produce high-quality writing with a competent mastery of grammar. Students must master grammar competency at the high school level. Although the teacher uses some strategies, some students still have problems understanding the material. Grammar is cen-

tral to teaching and learning language. Without grammar, teaching and learning are not able to develop knowledge successfully. It is one of the more difficult aspects of language to teach well. Ellis (2006) states that teaching

grammar is undoubtedly necessary for mastering the language and achieving accuracy and fluency. Although grammar is necessary for appropriate language usage, American students rarely learn its basic structures and functions formally or even informally. Suppose they have learned explicit grammar rules and structures. In that case, they usually learn it alongside something else (Micciche, 2004), especially since the current best strategy in modern education for teaching grammar to high school students is to incorporate it into writing and reading instruction. Because of this integrative mentality, US research rarely extracts opinions on grammar as a subject, tool, and part of life. In addition, since English is their native language, the United States has no consensus on a standard way of teaching English or its grammar, which leads to divided ideologies. In China, a study conducted by Ju Liu (2018) found that the effectiveness of junior middle school students in English grammar learning is very low, and teachers' current teaching strategies cannot meet the standard of students' communicative competence. Besides, the survey results demonstrate a significant demand for teachers to encourage students to improve the efficiency and accuracy of English grammar from reading. In order to improve learners' proficiency and accuracy and facilitate the internalization of its syntactic system in grammar teaching, teachers of English are supposed to encourage students to read classics, try to use integrated teaching methods rationally, guide explicit and implicit teaching respectively, and point out students' errors skillfully. Students with

positive and effective learning strategies are likelier to possess appropriate comprehensive ability and communicative competence. More-

over, in the Philippines, English has long been a part of the curricula of varied academic programs. The curriculum has changed drastically, but learning English remains an essential part of any curriculum. Despite the economic benefits of being an English-speaking nation, Filipinos have not fully maximized its potential. Studies show that the Filipinos' grasp of the English language is slipping while other Asians are catching up fast. In 2008, an online article by Karl Wilson in "The National" revealed that Filipinos scored an overall mean of 6.69 for the macro skills in English in terms of listening, writing, reading, and speaking. This indicates a rather low profile against the backdrop of international standards. Historically, the English proficiency of Filipinos has been consistently stable from 1993 to 2000 before a gradual decline was reported in the following years. Even more alarming is the rising percentage of those who are incompetent in English, which doubled from a measly 7% In Metro Manila, a study conducted by Pulse Asia in 2008 revealed that the grammar performance of public secondary high school teachers and students (especially those in first and second years) is below average. According to Tafida Okunade (2016), From primary school to the university level, many students are noted in their speech and writing as not being able to abide by the rules of subject-verb agreement. Errors in subject-verb agreement were found not only in students' essays but even in the writings of colleagues in universities. The more worrisome dimension of this problem is that such fiasco extends even to professionals who

use English in their lectures, those among the honorable members of state and national assemblies, or those engaged in varied media outfits. Errors in subject-verb agreement are becoming widespread, and it seems as if many people are either no longer aware of the rules or they undermine the importance of grammar rules for as long as they can convey their mes-

sage. Locally, in Daval Del Sur, although the rules on grammar have been introduced to students as early as their primary education, they still face problems acquiring linguistic competence in their communicative command or use of English. Apparently, the observed deterioration among students in their application or usage of correct grammar in the English language pervades those at the elementary and secondary levels of education. Since K to 12 uses spiral progression, the grammar competencies were expected to be mastered by the learners in the early stages as a prerequisite for them to cope with the more advanced grammar lessons in the higher levels of their education. The job market was becoming increasingly competitive. The workforce seems to have very strict qualifications. In addition to the job seekers' attitude toward work, one of the most important standards that employers are searching for is the applicants' competency in using English confidently, correctly, and fluently. To help respond to this alarming status of English language learning, the researcher decided to conduct this study. This study aims to explore the challenges of English teachers in improving the grammar competence of Junior High School students. This

study may serve as the primary basis for developing

appropriate learning resource materials and revitalization of grammar instructions that may arrest the overarching issue in English grammar. Further, it may provide some information on the competence of the future graduates of higher education institutions in terms of their English grammar proficiency, which was expected of them by prospective employers as shown by the employment requirements advertised in various newspapers

1.1. Purpose of the Study—This research aimed to explore the challenges English teachers face in improving the grammar competence of junior high school students. The researcher believed that this may help the students identify their weaknesses and strengths when it comes to studying and learning English grammar. Also, teachers, future educators, and administrators of educational institutions would gain some pointers on how to make English grammar learning more manageable, not fearsome. Coping mechanisms for the challenges are also included in the study to holistically identify educational management insights drawn from the study's findings.

- (1) What are the challenges of teachers in improving students' grammatical competence?
- (2) How do teachers cope with the challenges of improving students' grammatical competence?
- (3) What educational management insights are drawn from the experiences of teachers?

The following persons or agencies would be the beneficiaries to determine the outcomes of this study and to whom the findings were addressed. Department of Education. The study's findings may help the department refine and update language curricula, ensuring that grammar instruction is effective, relevant, and up-to-date. The study may also provide valuable data and insights for the department to make informed decisions on language instruction policies and practices. Teachers. Teachers may benefit from

the study by gaining insights into the most effective instructional methods for improving students' grammatical competence. This may inform their professional development and teaching strategies. The study may help teachers identify areas of difficulty for students and develop targeted interventions to address grammatical challenges effectively. It may also contribute to the development of better teaching materials and resources to support grammar instruction. Students. A study focused on enhancing

grammatical competence may lead to improved communication skills, making it easier for students to express their thoughts and ideas clearly and accurately. Students may be motivated to improve and increase engagement in their grammar competence as it is essential for academic achievement across subjects; it facilitates effective writing, reading comprehension, and critical thinking. 8 The following terms were operationally defined to make this study more comprehensive. Grammatical competence. Refers to a person's ability to use grammar effectively and accurately in spoken and written language. It was a crucial aspect of language proficiency and communication. Grammatical competence involves understanding and applying the rules and conventions of grammar, such as sentence structure, verb tense, word order, agreement, and punctuation. Pedagogical instructions refer to the methods, strategies, and approaches used by educators to facilitate effective teaching and learning experiences. These instructions aim to enhance students' understanding, engagement, and mastery of the subject matter. Pedagogical instructions encompass various techniques and practices that cater to students' diverse learning styles and needs.

1.2. Review of Related Literature—

1.2.1. English Grammatical Competence—

Grammatical competence, one of the key communicative competencies, is essential for effective communication in writing and speech (Murcia et al., 2000). It includes knowledge of grammatical rules, vocabulary, pronunciation, and spelling, and it plays a crucial role in second language teaching (Ma'mun, 2015; Purpura, 2005). Effective communication requires correct grammatical form to convey meaning accurately (Brown, 2004).

1.2.2. Teaching of Grammatical Competence—

Teachers should focus on both form and context, allowing students time to practice common grammatical patterns (Evans St. Jhon, 2012; Nunan, 2000). Grammatical competence

includes structural grammar, which analyzes word changes and sentence usage, and transformational grammar, which adapts basic sentences into various forms (Kolln Funk, 2010). It encompasses linguistic competence, including lexis, phonology, syntax, and morphology, and is necessary for students to communicate effectively in writing and speech (Fulcher Davidson, 2007).

1.2.3. Subject-Verb Agreement—

Subject-verb agreement is fundamental for sentence coherence. It ensures the subject and verb match in number (Sullivan, 2012; McLean, 2013). Errors often occur when clauses intervene between subject and verb, making it vital to identify the subject correctly (Mudrak, 2014; Huda, 2015). Advanced learners and native speakers can struggle with this concept, especially with the 3rd person singular –s (Vaurula, 2012).

1.2.4. Development of Learning Material—

Effective language programs require well-developed learning materials that align with teaching objectives and student needs (Patel, 2017; Kellough, 2009). Materials should be grounded in an instructional philosophy that suits the learners. The development of such materials is recognized as a critical aspect of applied research in language education (Tomlinson, 2016).

1.2.5. Coping Strategies in Improving Students' Grammatical Competence—

Grammar knowledge should be taught in rich, real contexts to facilitate understanding and application (Xiao, 2019). Teachers should employ a variety of methods, including communicative and task-based language teaching, to make grammar instruction engaging and effective (Ji Liu, 2018). Error correction should be handled skillfully, using explicit or implicit methods to enhance students' awareness and accuracy in grammar (Hedge, 2002).

Other Studies on Grammatical Competence Grammar is integral to language, acting as the pillar of communication competence (Wilkins,

2007; Feldman; Gleason, 2006). Mastery of grammar rules enables students to produce authentic, meaningful language (Carillo, 2008).

1.3. *Theoretical Lens*—Understanding language theories that underlie daily grammar teaching was significant for English teachers to have a basic knowledge of language acquisition theories as it directly influences their ability to provide appropriate content-area instructions. Chomsky (2005) states that the Theory of Competence was a system of linguistic knowledge possessed by native speakers of a language that makes it possible for them to produce and understand an infinite number of sentences in their language and to distinguish grammatical sentences from ungrammatical sentences. When a person has the knowledge of grammatical rules necessary for understanding and producing grammatically correct sentences, that person demonstrates grammatical competence. A person needs to have a good working knowledge of English grammar rules because it would make him appear intelligent and educated and give him credibility. Moreover, if he was looking for a job with great command of the English language and great grammar proficiency, he will have a clear advantage over someone whose grammar skills are below average. The Behaviorism Theory of Watson (1913), as indicated by Wijayanti (2012), is a psychology theory initiated by Watson as a reaction to traditional grammar. This theory was a systematic psychological approach to understanding human and animal behavior. Human behavior is generally a result of stimulus-response actions and states that people acquire behaviors through interaction with the environment. Behaviorism theory on educating human beings is based on the notion that behavior is controlled through positive and negative reinforcement. Behaviorism views imitation and practice as primary processes in language development; it resembles children learning their first language, where they imitate and practice other sounds and words in

their attempts to start speaking. Thus, children receive positive reinforcements from adults to encourage them to communicate and learn the language. This theory is based on the habit formation of language teaching. It resembles the learning of traditional or explicit grammar language learning, as it ignores language learning and problem-solving instead of the information and performance of habits. Alissa (2003) states that this theory places learners as individual and passive with its heavy reliance on a stimulus-response model. Two common characteristics of Behaviorism in teaching are the teacher-centered role, wherein students tend to be passive, and standardized tests to measure students' behavioral responses. Demirezen (2000) illustrates that there are some postulates when integrating behaviorism theory in teaching a second language, where learning is based on imitation, reinforcement, and rewards. In addition, he adds that imitation helps acquire basic vocabulary and sentences; however, different studies found that learning language through imitation resulted in no invitations. Imitation is significant in the initial stages of learning. Behaviorism is learning a second language based on generalizations in language learning where learners imitate or model teachers' sentences through habit formation or drill exercises. It hinders students' ability to innovate or produce instinctive language daily. Behaviorism theory would lead to delays in improving speech and hindering creative learning. However, some linguists believe that this theory is constructive in the early stages of language learning, especially for young children. Another theory is the Constructivism Theory of Piaget (1973), cited by Brooks Brooks (2000). Constructivism theory rejects perceiving learners' knowledge as a direct reflection of reality and that every individual can independently construct their validity. Learners acquire language through experience and practice related to the real world. The classroom comprises a collaborative discus-

Fig. 1. Conceptual framework of the study

sion between teachers and students where they can improve their critical thinking. Constructivism has very significant implications in the field of language teaching. Language learning can occur when language is used to communicate socially. Learners' roles shift from passive to active as they interact individually and construct meaning and learning. Marlowe and Page (2005) illustrate that this theory concerning language acquisition is built upon creating knowledge, not receiving it. In addition, constructivism in SLA (Second Language Acquisition) is about thinking and analyzing, not accumulating and memorizing the language. Another concept of Vygotsky's (1962) ZPD (Zone of Proximal Development) refers to the cognitive development that occurs through the interaction between a learner and other knowledgeable peers or teachers. He posits that learners can extend their knowledge if provided with a

space for social interaction, in which they can improve from those interactions, which means that knowledge is different from learning. In addition, engaging learners in authentic, goal-oriented activities to help them internalize academic concepts and creating "structured mediational spaces where they can develop their teaching skills are thus among the main premises on which sociocultural teacher education is based" Johnson Golombek (2020). The conceptual framework of the study is presented in Figure 1. Based on the figure, there were two interconnected working themes. These variables are the (1) challenges of teachers in improving students' grammatical competence, (2) teachers coping with the challenges of improving students' grammatical competence, and (3) educational management insights drawn from the experiences of teachers.

2. Methodology

This chapter of the study presented the method, research participants, data collection, role of the researcher, data analysis, trustworthiness of the study, and ethical considerations. Exploring facts and knowledge in this study necessitated the consequent design and implementation. Artificial intelligence (AI) was used for proofreading, as it is a common ethical practice in many articles today.

2.1. Philosophical Assumptions of the Study—The philosophical assumption is a framework used to collect, analyze, and interpret data in a specific field. It establishes the background for the following conclusions and decisions. Typical philosophical assumptions have different types, which are elaborated below. Ontology. This part of the research pertained to how the issue relates to the nature of reality. According to Creswell (2012), the reality was subjective and multiple, as the study participants saw. The ontological issue addressed the nature of reality for the qualitative researcher. The reality was constructed by individuals involved in the research situation. Thus, multiple realities exist, such as the realities of the researcher, those of individuals being investigated, and those of the reader or audiences interpreting the study. In this study, the challenges of English teachers in improving the grammar competence of Junior High School students were explored. In this study, the researcher relied on the voices and interpretations of the participants through extensive quotes and themes that reflected their words and provided evidence of different perspectives. The participant's answers to the study were coded and analyzed to build and construct the commonality and discreteness of responses. The participants' responses were carefully coded to ensure the reliability of the result. The researcher upheld the authenticity of the responses and precluded from making personal bias as the study progressed. Epistemology. This referred to the awareness of how knowledge claims were justified by staying as close to the participants as possible during the study to obtain firsthand information. Guba and Lincoln, as cited by Creswell (2012), stated that the researcher attempted to lessen the distance between himself or herself and the participants on the epistemological assumption. He suggested that, as a researcher, he or she collaborates, spends time in the field with participants, and becomes an 'insider'. This study intended

to gather information on the challenges English teachers face in improving the grammar competence of junior high school students. It was assured that close interaction with the participants was established to gain direct information that would shed light on the knowledge behind the inquiry. Axiology refers to the role of values in research. Creswell (2012) averred that the role of values in a study was significant. Axiology suggests that the researcher openly discusses values that shape the narrative and includes their interpretation in conjunction with participants' interpretation. The researcher ensured the dignity and value of every detail of information obtained from the participants. The researcher understood the personal and value-laden nature of the information gathered from the study. Therefore, the researcher preserved the merit of the participants' answers and carefully interpreted the answers in light of the participants' interpretation. Rhetoric. This philosophical assumption stressed that the researcher wrote in a literary, informal style using the personal voice, qualitative terms, and limited definitions. The researcher used the first person to elucidate Supreme Pupil Government (SPG) advisers on student leaders' servant leadership behavior in the study context.

2.2. Qualitative Assumptions—The methodology was different from the method. Methodology was a creative and responsive approach to understanding questions and subject matter, while method refers to the exact knowledge and procedure (Gerodias, 2013). This study explored English teachers' challenges in improving the grammar competence of Junior High School students, particularly those of Felipe-Innocencia Delua National High School, Sulop District, Division of Davao Del Sur. The researcher's drive to know the deeper meaning of their experiences became the basis for doing qualitative research, which was considered helpful in looking for "meanings and motivations that underline cultural

symbols, personal experiences, and phenomena.” By using phenomenology, this need was hoped to be addressed by bringing the stories of the English teachers in a manner that, as David (2005) wrote, the themes, symbols, and meaning of the experiences were presented. Phenomenological research was based on two premises. The first was that experience is a valid, rich, and rewarding source of knowledge; this experience is a source of knowledge and shapes one’s behavior. From the definition, human experience was viewed as a cornerstone of knowledge about human phenomena and not an unreliable source. The second premise of phenomenological research was that the everyday world was a valuable and productive source of knowledge, that we could learn much about ourselves and reap key insights into the nature of an event by analyzing how it occurs in our daily lives (Morrissey Higgs, 2006). By doing phenomenology, which concerns the “what” and the “how” (Moustakas, 1995), the researcher projected that the subjective experiences, challenges, and coping mechanisms of the English teachers were explored, and insights were drawn as a basis for possible future research and policy analysis about this research.

2.3. Design and Procedure—This study employed a qualitative approach to research, specifically a phenomenological research design, since it focused on the perspectives of English teachers on students’ grammatical competence. According to Creswell (2012), phenomenology was an approach to qualitative research that focuses on the commonality of lived experiences within a particular group. The fundamental goal of the approach is to describe the nature of the particular phenomenon. Typically, interviews were conducted with individuals with first-hand knowledge of an event, situation, or experience. Other forms of data, such as documents, observations, and art, were also used. The data were read and reread and were culled for phrases and themes that were grouped

into clusters of meanings. Through this process, the researcher was able to construct the universal meaning of the event, situation, or experience and arrived at a more profound understanding of the phenomenon. Moreover, Maxwell (2013) added that phenomenology, rooted in philosophy, psychology, and education, attempted to extract the purest, untainted data. In some interpretations of the approach, the researcher used bracketing to document personal experiences with the subject to help remove him or her from the process. One method of bracketing is taking notes. According to Corbetta (2003), the phenomenological research design was a qualitative type of research for which interviews provided an in-depth method that granted access to deep knowledge and explanations and helped grasp the subjects’ perspective. Creswell (2012) also claimed that qualitative research primarily used interviews. They occurred when researchers asked one or more participants general, open-ended questions and recorded their answers. Often, audio tapes were utilized to allow more consistent transcription. Interviews were also useful for following up with individual respondents after questionnaires, such as further investigating their responses. In qualitative research, interviews were used to pursue the meanings of central themes in the world of their subjects. The main task in doing interviews was to understand the meaning of what the interviewees said (McNamara, 1999). Based on Quad’s (2016) statements, the researcher transcribed and typed the data into a computer file to analyze it after the interview. Interviews were beneficial for uncovering the story behind a participant’s experiences and pursuing in-depth information about a topic. The researcher collected data from individuals who have experienced the phenomenon under investigation, typically via long interviews. Next, the data analysis involved triangulation, extracting significant statements from the transcribed interviews. The significant statements were transformed into

clusters of meanings according to how each statement fell under specific psychological and phenomenological concepts. Moreover, these transformations were tied together to make a general description of the experience, the textual description of what was experienced, and the structural description of how it was experienced. The researcher incorporated his or her meaning of the experiences here. Finally, the report was written so that readers could better understand the essential, invariant structure of the essence of the experience. Conversely, several challenges have been pointed out. The researcher required a solid grounding in the philosophical guidelines of phenomenology. The subjects selected for the study were individuals who have experienced the phenomenon. The researcher needed to bracket his or her experiences and observations, which were difficult. The researcher also needed to decide how and when his or her observations were incorporated into the study. Epistemologically, phenomenological approaches were based on the paradigm of personal knowledge and subjectivity and emphasized the importance of personal perspective and interpretation. As such, they were powerful tools for understanding subjective experience, gaining insights into people's motivations and actions, and cutting through the cluster of taken-for-granted assumptions and conventional wisdom. Since the focus of this study was to explore and assess the experiences of English teachers regarding students' grammatical competence, the researcher intended to employ phenomenological qualitative research methods.

2.4. Ethical Considerations—Ethical considerations were significant in the design of this research study. The researcher needed to consider several ethical issues regarding the research participant in this fieldwork. Ethical considerations were specified as one of the most important parts of the research. The researcher needed to adhere to the research aims, imparting authentic knowledge, truth, and error preven-

tion. Social Value. The research was essential to society. In this study, the social value was focused on teachers' experiences. This study was conducted explicitly among English teachers. This study also served as a basis for the higher authorities to create more programs and resolutions from which classroom teachers could benefit. Informed Consent. In the conduct and practice of this study, the Treaty Principle of Participation, as cited by McLeod (2009), was adhered to. The invitation to the participants ensured that their participation in the research was completely voluntary and based on understanding adequate information. The recruitment and selection of participants are lodged in the appendices of this study. Gaining the trust and support of research participants was critical to informed and ethical academic inquiry and phenomenological research (Walker, 2007, as cited by Pillerin, 2012). All participants were given an informed consent form before scheduling the interviews and participating in the phenomenological research process. Each participant was required to provide a signed personal acknowledgment, consent, and an indication of a willingness to participate in the study release. The purpose of the informed consent letter was to introduce the research effort, provide contact information, articulate the study's intent, request voluntary participation by the recipients, and anticipate the information the informants were expected to provide. All participants were required to sign and return the consent letter to the researcher before participating. Vulnerability of Research Participants. The participants of this study could answer the research instrument, for they were all professional teachers in public schools. Thus, the researcher assured them that as the researcher, he or she could easily be reached through the contact number and be addressed in case there were some clarifications or questions about the study. Risks, Benefits, and Safety. The recruitment of the respondents was free of coercion, undue influence, or induce-

ment. Moreover, respondents were provided with the contact numbers of the panel chair or panel members in case they had queries related to the study. Furthermore, if respondents experienced potential discomfort and inconvenience while answering the questions, they were not compelled to participate in any manner. Further, the researcher ensured the respondents were safe during the survey and interview. Thus, the questionnaire was distributed in a safe venue and administered conveniently. The dominant concern of this study is the Treaty Principle of Protection, as reflected in the respect for the rights of privacy and confidentiality and the minimization of risk. This was done by assigning pseudonyms for each informant so as not to disclose their identity. The possibility of a degree of risk inherent to this was minimized by taking all reasonable steps to guarantee participant confidentiality. Privacy and Confidentiality of Information. This study observed the Data Privacy Act of 2002 to ensure that the data cannot be traced back to their real sources to protect participants' identities. Thus, utmost care was taken to ensure the anonymity of the data sources. Hence, any printed output that was carried out from this study was kept in anonymity. Furthermore, all the issues were considered to avoid a conflict of interest between the researcher and the respondents. Any misleading information and representation of primary data findings in a biased way were avoided. Justice. The respondents were informed of the researcher's role and their corresponding role during data gathering. They were briefed that they had to give their full honesty in answering the survey questions, and additionally, any communication about the research was done with honesty. Similarly, they were informed that they would benefit first from the study results. Transparency. The study's results were accessed by the respondent's heads of the participating schools because the information was available and placed on CDs or other storage devices, which could be requested from

the researcher. In addition, by learning from the study results, participants were aware of the significance of the study and its contribution to their well-being. Further, each participant was advised that they have the right to withdraw their information at any time up to the completion of the data collection process. They could be requested and allowed to verify their transcript after the interview. This allowed the participants to amend or remove any information they felt might identify them. The researcher reserved the right to use pseudonyms and change names and/or non-significant dates to protect the participant's identity in all subsequent data analysis and reporting. Qualification of the Researcher. The researcher ensured that he or she was qualified to conduct the study. The researcher completed the academic requirements, passed the comprehensive examination before thesis writing, the last requirement to obtain the master's degree, and was qualified to conduct the study physically, mentally, emotionally, and financially. In addition, the advisee-adviser tandem ensured that the study reached its completion. Adequacy of Facilities. The researcher strived to complete the study successfully in the specified time and was equipped with the necessary resources. Likewise, the technical committee helped enhance the paper by giving suggestions and recommendations for improving the study. Also, the researcher ensured that he or she had enough funds to continue and finish the research. Thus, it was hoped that this study would be completed within the target time. Community Involvement. The researcher respected the respondents' local traditions, culture, and views in this study. Moreover, this study did not use deceit in any stage of its implementation, specifically in recruiting the participants or data collection methods. Furthermore, the researcher expressed great pleasure in the interviewees' wholehearted participation in the study. Plagiarism and Fabrication as the researcher. The researcher respected other works

by properly citing the author and rewriting what someone else had said his or her way. The researcher also used quotes to indicate that the text had been taken from another paper. Similarly, the researcher assured that honesty was present when working on the manuscript and that no intentional misrepresentation and making up of data or results was included or that conclusions were purposefully put forward that were not accurate.

2.5. Research Participants—The participants of this study were the eight (8) English teachers of Felipe-Innocencia Deluao National High School, Sulop District, Division of Davao Del Sur. The participants were chosen based on the following criteria: (1) must be in the present position for at least 5 years- regardless of their age, sex, and marital status; (2) must be teaching English subjects in Grade 8; (3) and must have at least a very satisfactory rating in IPCRF. The researcher utilized the purposive sampling design since the participants were chosen based on the criteria or purpose of the study (Creswell, 2014). It was also known as judgmental, selective, or subjective sampling. The selection of the participants was purposefully done to ensure that the findings were authentic (Marshall, 1996).

2.6. Research Instrument—In gathering data, the researcher utilized an in-depth interview questionnaire. The researcher developed the interview questionnaire, which was answered by the participants orally. These researcher-made interview questionnaires were developed upon consultation and validation by the experts and underwent several processes to accommodate their suggestions. The validated components include the language and the conceptual levels of questions if suited to the participant's level of understanding, the suitability of the items to the research design in which there should be no leading questions, and the alignment of the interview questions to the study's objective.

2.7. Data Collection—The following was the step-by-step process of gathering the data needed. Asking permission from the Schools Division Superintendent. In September 2023, the researcher asked permission from the Schools Division Superintendent to conduct the study in the identified school. The researcher sent a letter addressed to the Schools Division Superintendent with Chapters 1 and 2 attached, together with the research instrument, which explained the study's objectives and the participants' identification. The researcher waited for the SDS's response before conducting the study. Asking permission from the school heads. In the same month, after securing the approval of the SDS, the researcher sent letters to the principals of the schools explaining the study to be conducted in their schools. Obtaining consent from the participants. Still, in September 2023, the researcher asked permission from the participants. They were formally oriented about the study and the process they shall go through as participants. Conducting the interview. In September, the researcher conducted an in-depth interview using the interview questionnaire. The profile of the participants was taken, notes were jotted down, and conversations were recorded using a sound recorder for ease of transcription. The researcher carefully listened and responded actively during the interviews. Transcribing the interviewees' responses. In December 2023, the researcher transcribed the interviewees' responses precisely by recalling their answers from the sound recorder. Since the participants used their vernacular language, the researcher translated it into English. Data Coding and thematizing. In January 2024, after the transcription, the data were categorized and coded. Then, themes were extracted, and individual participant data were compared and contrasted. The researcher then conducted a second round of interviews (FGD) to corroborate any data that needed further explanation and input from the participants. Additional in-

formation gathered was examined thoroughly and integrated into the existing body of data. After this, data were compared and contrasted between the participants to develop patterns and trends.

2.8. *Data Analysis*—In this study, thematic analysis was utilized to analyze the gathered data. The researcher analyzed the participants' answers from the interviews using Creswell's Model, specifically the identifying of themes approach. According to Creswell (2012), themes in qualitative research were similar codes aggregated together to form a significant idea in the database. Familiarization with the data was common to all forms of qualitative analysis. The researcher immersed herself in and became intimately familiar with their data, reading and re-reading it and noting any initial analytic observations. Coding was also a common element of many approaches to qualitative analysis. It involved generating pithy labels for essential features of the data relevant to the (broad) research question guiding the analysis. Coding was not simply a data reduction method; it was also an analytic process, so codes captured both a semantic and conceptual reading of the data. The researcher coded every data item and ended this phase by collating all their codes and relevant data extracts. Searching for themes was a coherent and meaningful pattern in the data relevant to the research question. The researcher ended this phase by collating all the coded data relevant to each theme. Reviewing themes. The researcher reflected on whether the themes tell a convincing and compelling story about the data and began to define the nature of each theme and the relationship between the themes. Defining and naming themes: The researcher prepared a detailed analysis of each theme, identifying the 'essence' of each theme and constructing a concise, punchy, and informative name for each theme. Writing up involved weaving together the analytic narrative and data extracts to tell the reader a coherent

and persuasive story about the data and contextualizing it about existing literature. The researcher made sure that the experiences of English teachers in improving the grammar competence of Junior High School students were presented comprehensively.

2.9. *Analytical Framework*—The framework analysis of this research was flexible to allow the researcher to either collect all the data and then analyze it or do data analysis during the collection process. The gathered data was sifted, charted, and sorted under key issues and themes in the analysis stage. This involved a five-step process: (1) familiarization, (2) identifying a thematic framework, (3) indexing, (4) charting, and (5) mapping and interpretation (Ritchie Spencer, 1994). Familiarization refers to the process during which the researcher became familiarized with the transcripts of the data collected (i.e., interview or focus group transcripts, observation, or field notes) and gained an overview of the collected data (Ritchie Spencer, 1994). In other words, the researcher became immersed in the data by listening to audiotapes, studying the field, or reading the transcripts. Throughout this process, the researcher became aware of key ideas and recurrent themes and noted them. Due to the sheer volume of data collected in qualitative research, the researcher could not review all of the material. Thus, a selection of the data set was utilized. The selection depended on several aspects of the data collection process—for example, a mix of methods can be used (e.g., interviews, documents, observations). The second stage, identifying a thematic framework, occurs after familiarization, when the researcher recognizes emerging themes or issues in the data set. These emerging themes or issues had arisen from a priori themes. Were issues. However, the researcher allowed the data to dictate the themes and issues at this stage. The researcher used the notes taken during the familiarization stage to achieve this end. The key issues, concepts,

Fig. 2. Illustrates the descriptive phenomenological data analysis process created by Colaizzi (1978).

and themes expressed by the participants now formed the basis of a thematic framework used to filter and classify the data (Ritchie Spencer, 1994). Indexing meant identifying portions or sections of the data that corresponded to a particular theme. This process was applied to all the textual data that had been gathered from transcripts of interviews. For convenience, Ritchie and Spencer recommend that a numerical system be used to index references and annotate them in the margin beside the text (1994). Qualitative data analysis tools were ideal for such a task. The final stage, mapping and interpretation, involved the analysis of the key characteristics as laid out in the charts. This analysis provided a schematic diagram of the event/phenomenon, thus guiding the researcher in his/her interpretation of the data set. At this point, the researcher was cognizant of the objectives of qualitative analysis: “defining concepts, mapping range and nature of phenomena, creating typologies, finding associations, providing explanations, and developing strategies” (Ritchie Spencer, 1994). Once again, these concepts, technologies, and associations reflected the participant. Therefore, the researcher’s strategy

or recommendations echoed the participants’ actual attitudes, beliefs, and values. To summarize, the thematic analysis method outlined by Braun and Clarke (2006) consisted of six (6) phases used in analyzing the data. The following steps represent the Colaizzi process for phenomenological data analysis (cited in (Sanders, 2003; Speziale Carpenter, 2007); Each transcript should be read and re-read to obtain a general sense of the whole content; significant statements about the phenomenon under study should be extracted from each transcript. these statements must be recorded on a separate sheet, noting their page and line numbers; meanings should be formulated from these significant statements, and the formulated meanings should be sorted into categories, clusters of themes, and themes; the findings of the study should be integrated into an exhaustive description of the phenomenon under study; the fundamental structure of the phenomenon should be described. Finally, validation of the findings should be sought from the research participants to compare the researcher’s descriptive results with their experiences.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents and discusses the study's results with reference to its aim. It also discusses the themes that emerged from the data gathered. The results present the description and background of the participants who were assigned pseudonyms to conceal their identities.

3.1. Challenges of Teachers in Improving Students' Grammatical Competence—For decades, the role of grammar instruction in an English curriculum has been a major issue for students and teachers alike. Researchers have debated whether grammar should be taught in the classroom, and students, for their part, have generally considered grammar instruction a necessary evil at best and an avoidable burden at worst (Al-Mekhlafi Navaratnam, 2009). Teachers play a pivotal role in language education, shaping students' grammatical competence. However, this endeavor is not without its challenges. This section delves into teachers' multifaceted difficulties when attempting to enhance students' grammatical proficiency. The teachers' responses were narrowed down into one to generate themes and subthemes. These were carefully analyzed and formulated based on informants' accounts and reflections.

3.1.1. Poor attitude towards grammar instructions—The participants claimed the biggest challenge is when the learners see their grammar lessons as difficult and tedious. A student's attitude is an integral part of learning, and it should become an essential component of second or foreign-language learning pedagogy. The reason is that attitude influences one's behaviors, inner mood, and learning. So, it is clear that there is an interaction between language learning and the environmental components in which the student grows up. Both negative and positive attitudes strongly impact the success of language learning. In addition, the participants claimed that students' confidence level in performing in grammar lessons affects their learning development and interest in the topic. when students find grammar lessons diffi-

cult, it can negatively impact their self-esteem and belief in their ability to master language skills. The responses of the participants validate the findings of Le Le (2022) that internal and external factors affected the students' attitudes. Regarding the internal factors, students' self-confidence, risk-taking willingness, anxiety, curiosity, and awareness of the importance of English in their future considerably impacted their attitudes toward English learning. As a solution, a "communicative" way of teaching grammar is advisable rather than using the traditional strategy (Ban, 2018). Grammar must be presented contextually. Teaching and learning grammar must be followed through guided practice. This practice enables the students to develop and enhance their language. There are several reasons why research on students' attitudes toward grammar learning is essential. First, attitudes toward learning are believed to influence behaviors such as selecting and reading books and speaking in a foreign language. Second, a relationship between attitudes and success or achievement has been shown to exist. Attitudes influence achievement rather than achievement influencing attitudes. The reason is that attitude influences one's behaviors, inner mood, and learning. So, it is clear that there is an interaction between language learning and the environmental components in which the student grows up. Both negative and positive attitudes substantially impact the success of language learning (Getie, 2019).

3.1.2. Diverse learning needs—The diverse spectrum of language proficiency levels within a single classroom presents a multifaceted challenge for educators. Students enter the learning space with varying degrees of

familiarity and mastery over grammatical structures, creating a rich but challenging instructional landscape. Teacher participants observed that some students demonstrate a robust understanding of grammar, seamlessly navigating complex concepts. In contrast, others may struggle with foundational elements that challenge them. The participants reported that these diverse needs may originate from students' backgrounds and exposure to English. Learners from diverse linguistic backgrounds may face distinct challenges, making implementing a one-size-fits-all instructional approach challenging.

Learning English grammar became problematic due to differences in students' abilities and competencies. Grammatical difficulty is, to some extent, associated with individual differences in language level. This is based on the view that learners with a more vital ability to learn languages may be better equipped to deal with grammatical difficulty in the second language than learners with weaker aptitude (Shiu, 2011). Petraki and Hill (2010) also claimed that English language learners have originated from different races and cultural backgrounds. These learners have various educational backgrounds and capabilities that provide different levels of knowledge based on their experiences. The differences in background, language learning experience, and teaching experience of students make the differences in grammar knowledge that the students accept. So, the abilities of the students to accept knowledge were different. According to Smith (2018), educators often grapple with the reality that students enter the classroom with diverse foundational language skills. These disparities can create a considerable challenge in maintaining a balanced instructional pace. Some students possess a solid grasp of basic language structures, while others may struggle with fundamental concepts, impacting their ability to engage with more advanced grammatical principles.

3.1.3. Limited vocabulary—The participants noticed that students have poor vocabulary skills. They have difficulty translating the vernacular words they want to write into English and also have difficulty in arranging it into proper sentences. For the participants, grammar is a complex intellectual task involving many component skills, and some of these are the vocabulary skills that at-risk students may lack completely or have only partially mastered.

The participants attributed these poor skills to the students' study habits. Most of them do not read many books or are not interested in reading, hence the poor acquisition of words. The student's level of motivation to grab a book, read, and learn new words is very low since there are many distractions surrounding them, making their priorities shift.

When students lack skills in these areas, their writing may be unsatisfactory— from poor grammar and syntax to unclear organization to weak reasoning and arguments. Complicating matters is that many at-risk students' reading skills are also poor. The participants asserted that if they cannot recognize the main point of an argument in their reading, they obviously cannot respond to this point in their writing. The finding supports Mehring's (2005) idea that a good vocabulary foundation is an essential aspect of grammar skills. Complexities associated with vocabulary include learners failing to remember essential words to use, failing to use the appropriate words, and having a poor vocabulary. The acquisition of vocabulary is an ongoing process requiring the constant repetition and use of words by students to be effectively achieved in long-term memory. It is not sufficient to develop vocabulary by memorizing words from a list; for learners to acquire vocabulary, words must be learned in the context in which they occur. This method has proven to be useful because it helps the student understand the correct use of the word. In addition, the acquisition of vocabulary is a learner-centered

Fig. 3. Emerging Themes on the Challenges of Teachers in Improving Students' Grammatical Competence

activity, and the effectiveness of the strategies of the learner depends on his/her attitude and motivation for new vocabulary acquisition. As a result, vocabulary can significantly impact the importance and contribution to the value of writing ability for students. Therefore, learners are expected to have a positive attitude towards learning new vocabulary and, while trying to identify their meanings, recognize new words as part of their occurrence. Meanwhile, Bahri and Sugeng (2010) asserted that grammar is a fundamental element in every language and inseparable from writing. The primary complica-

tion of writing that students find about grammar is the common understanding of grammar, leading to difficulties in arranging good writing. The figure shows the emerging themes of teachers' challenges in improving students' grammatical competence. The themes were poor attitude towards grammar instructions, diverse learning needs, and limited vocabulary. These themes implied that teachers should adopt a holistic approach to instruction. Integrating engagement strategies, individualized instruction, and vocabulary development simultaneously can address multiple challenges.

3.2. *Teachers Coping with the Challenges of Improving Students' Grammatical Competence*—Learning grammar has been part of language skills since grammar is a fundamental feature of a language. If learners fail to understand grammar rules, they will fail to communicate effectively in that language. At every level of learning institution, the teaching of grammar is always perceived as the most challenging skill to teach and the most tedious skill to learn. Therefore, if grammar is mentioned in the classroom, it would cause students to have moments of anxiety. To overcome this, language instructors have to do their best to make grammar teaching as “non-threatening,

imaginative and helpful activity within the English curriculum. (Al-Mekhlafi Nagaratnam, 2011). This section presents the coping mechanism teachers use to improve students' grammatical competence. Their responses were narrowed down into one to generate themes and subthemes. These were carefully analyzed and formulated based on informants' accounts and reflections.

3.2.1. *Presenting grammar knowledge in rich and real contexts*—Grammar is essential to language learning, providing the structural framework that enables effective communication. Traditionally, grammar instruction has been associated with rigid rules, isolated ex-

ercises, and memorization. However, educators increasingly recognize the importance of presenting grammar knowledge in rich and real contexts to enhance learning outcomes. For the participants, presenting grammar within rich and real contexts allows students to see the immediate relevance of language rules in everyday communication. Real-context learning bridges theoretical knowledge and practical application, making grammar more meaningful and engaging for students. Teachers can demonstrate the real-life implications of grammatical structures by teaching grammar lessons in authentic situations, making them more memorable and applicable. Teaching grammar in a real context will allow students to understand how language works, which will improve their communication skills. They will see how it should be applied in the real world and find relevance to learning it. The responses of the participants relate to the research findings of Xiao (2019), which state that grammar knowledge is acquired through preliminary perception, overall understanding, and practical application of a large amount of real data. Teachers should provide students with abundant corpus and language performance scenarios instead of confining themselves to isolated explanations of examples and exercises. As advocated by the English Curriculum (2017), views on English grammar teaching are three-dimensional, dynamic, targeted at "form-meaning-use," and oriented by language use. Grammar participates in the transmission of the basic meaning of a discourse. The choice of grammatical form depends on the pragmatic meaning expressed in specific contexts, such as the speaker's intention, emotion, and attitude, as well as an understanding of participants' roles and identities. Therefore, in language teaching, teachers should attach great importance to presenting new grammatical knowledge in rich and real contexts and guide students to observe the occasions, forms of expression, basic meaning, and pragmatic functions of the grammatical

items they have learned in the context. Moreover, they should consolidate students' grammatical knowledge through in-class and after-class exercises and activities and guide students to use language forms accurately and appropriately (Xiao, 2019).

3.2.2. *Enhancing the systematicity, relevance, and fun of grammar teaching*—English grammar in senior high school covers many knowledge points and language rules, which are implemented in textbooks with a certain degree of systematicity and relevance. Teachers should change the fragmented and isolated teaching of grammar points in the past. Instead, they need to adopt the constructivist theory of language learning, familiarize themselves with the grammar knowledge involved in all stages of middle school English study, and build the connection between the known and unknown knowledge. The participants suggested that teachers use mind maps to sort out grammar points and establish connections to help students perceive grammar items in senior high school. At the same time, to enhance the fun of grammar teaching, teachers can add jokes, English songs, movies, information communication technologies, and so on so that students can learn grammar knowledge in interesting contexts and maintain long-term interest in learning. Furthermore, the participants believed this strategy could address the diverse needs of the students. The participants' responses validate the findings of Ji Liu (2018) that although English grammar teaching is not only an in-class task, there is no denying that effectiveness in the classroom is more critical than compensatory learning after class. In order to improve effectiveness in the classroom, teachers should actively explore effective and appropriate methods of grammar teaching, such as communicative teaching methods, task-based language teaching methods, guiding exploration teaching methods, cooperative teaching methods, technology-integrated methods, etc. Teachers should ratio-

nally use integrated teaching methods according to the specific situations and demands. That is to say, when dealing with different levels of grammar knowledge, teachers should skillfully change the one-centered teaching method and combine it with other corresponding teaching methods. For example, when explaining the usage of present progressive tense, teachers are advised to use the communicative teaching method as the one-centered method because communication can quickly acquaint students with the correct usage of present progressive tense. The teaching method should be adjusted to students' grammar learning situations. At the same time, students are supposed to cooperate with teachers to improve their learning strategies. Besides, it is widely recognized that a free, positive, and pleasant classroom communication environment contributes to higher learning efficiency. Teachers should not only teach grammar rules but also pay attention to the practical application of grammar and guide the students to cooperate with others to enhance their learning strategy and learn grammar more efficiently. Furthermore, grammar teaching should expand in-class work. For instance, teachers should give students more opportunities to engage in oral communication to improve their grammatical competence (Ji Liu, 2018).

3.2.3. Pointing out students' errors skillfully—Skillful error correction is a constructive tool for facilitating students' learning progression. Teachers guide students toward a deeper understanding of language rules by pinpointing specific grammar errors. This targeted feedback helps learners recognize their mistakes and guides to correct and improve their language use. Furthermore, the participants affirmed that error correction is not solely about pointing out mistakes; it also involves providing constructive feedback that builds students' confidence. For them, offering explanations, alternative expressions, and positive reinforcement, teachers create an environment where students feel sup-

ported rather than discouraged. This positive reinforcement encourages students to view errors as opportunities for growth rather than failures. The participants' responses verified the findings of Hedge (2002) that most students could not realize the grammatical errors in their conversations. Errors that are incorrect will eventually evolve into customary errors in future learning. Therefore, language classes must include error correction. Thus, during grammar teaching, teachers should pay attention to correct students' errors reasonably. There are generally two ways to correct students' errors: "explicit method" and "implicit method". The "explicit method" means that teachers explicitly point out what kind of grammatical mistakes students have made and point out the correct grammatical knowledge using analysis. The "implicit method" means that teachers should use various means to provide students with hints about the errors, helping students find them themselves. Some grammatical errors, such as lexical errors, are problematic for learners to perceive. Therefore, teachers should explicitly explain or implicitly guide students frequently to strengthen their awareness and concept of error correction in communications (Hedge, 2002). In this way, students' grammar learning accuracy will be significantly improved. In addition, as for the time to point out students' errors, teachers should attach great importance to the suitable time. Some severe and common grammar errors should be pointed out immediately in the classroom, while some minor errors can be pointed out after class. As teachers are not the only group to make corrections, peer and classmate corrections are also advisable in different situations. Teachers should learn how to effectively help students correct errors, taking their personality and the specific grammatical errors they make into account so that students can realize the errors consciously without hurting their self-esteem (Hedge, 2002).

Fig. 4. Emerging Themes on Teachers Coping with the Challenges of Improving Students' Grammatical Competence

The figure above shows the emerging themes of teachers coping with the challenges of improving students' grammatical competence. The themes were presenting grammar knowledge in rich and authentic contexts, enhancing the systematicity, relevance, and fun of grammar teaching, and skillfully pointing out students' errors. These themes implied that teachers could present grammar in rich contexts, ensuring relevance and real-world application while maintaining systematicity. Skillful error correction complements these efforts by providing individualized feedback and building students' confidence, addressing various facets of the learning process. The integration of these themes places students at the center of the learning experience. It acknowledges their diverse learning needs, fosters engagement, and encourages a positive attitude toward learning grammar. Teachers can empower students by creating an engaging, relevant, and supportive learning environment to manage the challenges of improving grammatical competence with enthusiasm and resilience.

3.3. Educational Management Insights Drawn from the Experiences of the Teachers— This section presents the participants' educational management insights. Their responses were narrowed down into one to generate themes and subthemes. These were carefully analyzed and formulated based on informants'

accounts and reflections.

*3.3.1. Sustained practice—*Consistent engagement in content writing is crucial for grammar development. Dedicating oneself to regular practice is imperative to attain proficiency in a new skill or behavior. The individuals emphasized that becoming a skilled writer does not happen overnight; accomplishing these objectives requires effort and time. Consequently, they advocate for English teachers to offer students chances to hone their writing skills gradually. As highlighted by the participants, establishing a routine to practice and assessing one's strengths and weaknesses as a writer is essential. Enabling students to engage in writing compositions allows teachers to instill a habit of outlining essay structures before delving into the actual writing process. This approach ensures that students incorporate all relevant points and crucial information into their papers. Furthermore, this habit aids them in concentrating on the structural aspects while independently practicing essay writing. Additionally, the participants believe that students need to practice right because practice makes it permanent. If the students practice the wrong writing and grammar, it will become a repetitive behavior that will be difficult to change. Hence, getting started with the proper practice will significantly impact performance.

The participants' responses corroborate with UAGC's (2021) assertion that engaging in grammatical practice contributes to an overall improvement in communication skills and enhances writing abilities, which are crucial for effective communication. The more one dedicates time to learning grammar, the easier it becomes to cultivate a distinctive and recognizable personal style. Like other skills, regular practice is key to making writing more effortless and impactful (UAGC, 2021). The practice that is repetitive in action that people do to learn a skill and then put it on the automatic pilot will, however, not improve grammar skills. Instead, according to Ericsson (2019), deliberate practice will harness the adaptability of the human brain to create, step by step, the ability to do previously impossible things. With this kind of practice, a person will build areas of the brain that involve grammar skills, increasing their talent and making themselves better writers and speakers. It requires setting goals for practice sessions, maintaining focus as they practice, getting feedback on the practice, pushing themselves out of their comfort zone, developing effective mental representations of the skills that they are practicing, and learning from models of excellence.

3.3.2. *Cultivate a love for reading*—Reading all types of writing can spark ideas in students' imaginations. The more they read fiction and creative nonfiction, the more they naturally adopt their natural rhythm and flow. The participants viewed reading as a way to help improve students' memory and overall cognitive function. Reading for them is jogging for the brain, one of the most effective ways students can exercise their grammar skills. With improved cognitive functioning comes improved abilities through a greater ability to make mental connections. Those with higher cognitive functioning can write and speak more grammatically correct structures and present ideas more clearly and comprehensively. Having a

broad reading experience can broaden students' awareness of the world. According to the participants, delving into various book genres allows students to better comprehend these diverse literary styles. This exposure enables students to enhance their perspectives and use grammar skills with a heightened sensitivity to a broader audience and various topics. Additionally, the participants asserted that immersing themselves in stories featuring diverse individuals fosters student empathy and awareness.

The participants expressed the need for every teacher, not just English teachers, to encourage students to read and develop strong reading habits. They should encourage students to read for both pleasure and mind investment.

The participants' responses corroborate with Zhes (2012) that addressing students' reading skills can also positively impact students' abilities, such as spelling, grammar, phonemic awareness, and phonics. Despite the common practice of teaching reading and writing as distinct subjects, students face challenges in completing grammar improvement tasks if they struggle to read and comprehend instructions. The interconnectedness of these skills underscores their equal importance in students' overall success. Given that many students dislike reading, the majority find the task relating to grammar improvement even more formidable. Hence, it becomes crucial to assist students in cultivating a reading habit to enhance their grammatical skills in both speaking and writing. Moreover, suppose students read more about what they are going to write about, discussing and analyzing the ideas in the materials at hand. In that case, they will develop many ideas for grammatical use in writing. Reading and writing will interact together to form the schemata of the reader. Hao and Sivell (2002) have analyzed the context of the reading/writing connection and the benefits students may gain. They assured that the texts should interest the learners to generate the desire for honest communication.

Moreover, introducing the materials and giving instruction around them will assist learners in gathering information to support, develop, and generate new ideas, and at the same time, they may extend their lexical and syntactical repertoire.

3.3.3. Instilling a positive learning environment—Feedback on performance in a grammar improvement activity is a deeply personal experience for students. When delivering this feedback, teachers should acknowledge the vulnerability and foster a positive environment that motivates students to enhance their skills rather than discourage them from trying. The participants recognize the significance of creating a positive learning environment when providing performance feedback on students' grammar skills. They also suggest that the classroom atmosphere predominantly shapes the students' performance. A nurturing classroom environment tends to yield positive and desired outcomes in the students' grammatical proficiency. To foster such a positive learning environment, the participants offered strategic recommendations to teachers. The participants' responses surround the idea that teachers have to acquire students' trust to guide them on their educational journey. Teachers must determine the best way to interact with each student, utilizing humor, technology, or other creative strategies to communicate their feedback. One-on-one meetings will help teachers show students that they care about them and are always there to assist them in their grammar improvement tasks. Furthermore, the participants implied that reinforcement of good behavior greatly contributes to effective feedback delivery. Reinforcement motivates the students to practice the desired behavior or performance in the grammar lessons. In general, the participants' responses relate to the study of Usman (2018). The author found that learning environments are crucial to stu-

dents' success in grammar development. Students who study grammar in a positive learning environment are more motivated, engaged in the task, and have higher skill development. The teacher's personality is an essential factor in the learning environment. They are key factors that create a favorable teaching-learning experience that will make grammar activity interesting, enthusiastically adaptable, and useful. When delivering feedback, teachers must ensure it is constructive, transparent, and non-biased. Another study supports the statements of the participants in the study of Strade, L. (2018) that the learning environment is a critical part of effective grammar instruction. A positive learning environment keeps students motivated to continue their work, provides appropriate instruction and feedback, and manages students' work so that they are on the path of targeting the goal or objective. The author also tackled that an effective teacher is an excellent classroom manager. Effective teaching and learning cannot take place in a poorly managed classroom. Therefore, teachers must ensure that students are in order to deliver what is expected of them. The figure shows the emerging themes of educational management insights from teachers' experiences improving students' grammatical competence. The themes were sustained practice, cultivating a love for reading, and instilling a positive learning environment. These themes implied a need for curriculum planning incorporating consistent opportunities for students to engage in activities promoting grammatical competence. Educational managers may need to ensure that curricula include regular and varied exercises for sustained practice. Teachers may consider implementing or supporting reading programs and initiatives within schools. This could involve investing in libraries, organizing literary events, and collaborating with community partners to create a reading-friendly culture.

Fig. 5. Emerging Themes on the Educational Management Insights drawn from the Experiences of the Teachers

4. Implications and Future Directions

This chapter presents a brief overview of the study, followed by implications based on its findings. Future directions in the participants’ experiences were also discussed here.

4.1. Implications—This research study aimed to explore the challenges of English teachers in improving the grammar competence of Junior High School students. The emerging themes of teachers’ challenges in improving students’ grammatical competence were poor attitude toward grammar instructions, diverse learning needs, and limited vocabulary. These themes implied that teachers should adopt a holistic approach to instruction. Integrating engagement strategies, individualized instruction, and vocabulary development simultaneously can address multiple challenges. Recognizing and addressing diverse learning needs require a move towards individualized instruction. Teachers should implement differentiated strategies, offering additional support to students with varying proficiency levels and adapting materials to suit different learning styles. Teachers must implement strategies to enrich students’ vocabulary. This can include incorporating daily vocabulary-building exercises, encouraging reading habits, and introducing challenging yet contextually relevant words. Moreover, teachers must employ creative and engaging strategies to shift students’ attitudes to-

ward grammar. Incorporating interactive activities, real-world applications, and multimedia resources can make grammar instruction more interesting. Meanwhile, the emerging themes on teachers coping with the challenges of improving students’ grammatical competence were presenting grammar knowledge in rich and authentic contexts, enhancing the systematicity, relevance, and fun of grammar teaching, and skillfully pointing out students’ errors. Teachers should integrate authentic and meaningful contexts into grammar lessons, emphasizing how language is used in real-life situations. This approach helps students understand the practical relevance of grammar rules in effective communication. They should adopt systematic approaches to present grammar rules, providing students with clear and organized learning paths. This enhances the systematicity of grammar teaching, making it more accessible and understandable. In addition, incorporating fun elements such as games, interactive activities, and multimedia into grammar teaching enhances student engagement and motivation. This approach transforms grammar from a potentially tedious subject into an enjoyable and stimulating learn-

ing experience. Furthermore, correcting errors involves providing constructive feedback that builds students' confidence. This positive reinforcement encourages a growth mindset, where students view errors as opportunities for improvement rather than failures. These themes implied that teachers could present grammar in rich contexts, ensuring relevance and real-world application while maintaining systematicity. Skillful error correction complements these efforts by providing individualized feedback and building students' confidence, addressing various facets of the learning process. The integration of these themes places students at the center of the learning experience. It acknowledges their diverse learning needs, fosters engagement, and encourages a positive attitude toward learning grammar. Teachers can empower students by creating an engaging, relevant, and supportive learning environment to manage the challenges of improving grammatical competence with enthusiasm and resilience. Lastly, on the educational management insights from teachers' experiences in improving students' grammatical competence, the themes were sustained practice, cultivating a love for reading, and instilling a positive learning environment. These themes implied a need for curriculum planning incorporating consistent opportunities for students to engage in activities promoting grammatical competence. Educational managers may need to ensure that curricula include regular and varied exercises for sustained practice. Teachers may consider implementing or supporting reading programs and initiatives within schools. This could involve investing in libraries, organizing literary events, and collaborating with community partners to create a reading-friendly culture. The themes suggest a need for allocating resources, both human and material, to support sustained practice initiatives. This may involve providing teachers with appropriate materials and tools to facilitate ongoing practice and create a conducive read-

ing and learning environment. Educational managers may need to explore assessment methods that align to improve grammatical competence through sustained practice. This could involve incorporating continuous assessment measures that reflect the student's progress over time. Further, to instill a positive learning environment, educational managers should focus on creating a supportive climate and culture within schools. This might involve promoting positive teacher-student relationships, implementing behavior management strategies, and fostering a culture of collaboration and respect.

4.1.1. Future Directions—Data obtained had future directions for various stakeholders in education, including policymakers, administrators, and teachers. The future directions of this study were as follows: Policymakers may allocate resources for ongoing professional development programs that equip teachers with effective strategies for grammar instruction. Continuous training ensures educators stay abreast of best practices. They may also implement policies that support technology integration in grammar instruction. Utilizing digital tools can make learning more engaging and interactive for students. School Principals may collaborate with educators to develop a well-rounded language curriculum that emphasizes sustained practice, reading initiatives, and positive learning environments to enhance grammatical competence. Moreover, allocate resources for acquiring grammar-focused instructional materials, reading resources, and technology tools. Ensure the availability of a well-equipped library and learning spaces that support language development. Teachers may employ differentiated teaching strategies to tailor instruction to meet students' diverse needs. They may recognize and address individual learning styles and levels of grammatical proficiency. They may infuse real-world contexts into grammar lessons to demonstrate the practical application of grammatical rules. They may also relate

grammar instruction to everyday communication to enhance student engagement. They may also commit to lifelong learning by staying updated on research, attending workshops, and engaging in professional development opportunities. This ensures that teachers remain effective in their grammar instruction. Moreover, future researchers may research innovative teaching methods, technology integration, and multimodal approaches that can provide valuable insights. They may also explore the influence of cultural and linguistic factors on grammatical competence. Research should consider how diverse cultural and linguistic backgrounds may impact the acquisition of grammatical skills. These recommended studies would yield advantageous findings and implications tailored to the organization and hierarchical context of the education sector.

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